

How to foster learning? By limiting the response speed.

Self-regulation and academic difficulties

Nowadays, many students experience difficulties to achieve basic competencies (OECD, 2016). In numerous countries, there is a great concern about the magnitude of school failure and about the number of students that have trouble at academic spheres. A large number of authors have pointed out that some of these academic difficulties are related to a lack of self-regulation (Barkley & Fischer, 2011; Barkley, 2012; Naglieri & Das, 2005; Núñez, González-Pienda & Carbonero, 1998; Rosário, Núñez, González-Pienda, Almeida, Soares y Rubio, 2005; Schunk & Zimmerman, 1998; Zimmerman, 2002).

Many definitions of self-regulation have been formulated. Panadero (2017) mentioned that self-regulated learning is a “core conceptual framework to understand the cognitive, motivational, and emotional aspects of learning” (p.422). Zimmerman (2002) defined self-regulation as a process by which students use their capacities in order to achieve academic success rather than as a crystallized mental ability or a single personal quality trait that someone has or not has. This author, along with Ramdass, emphasized the relevance of self-regulation skills not only to academic success but also to achieve a prosperous life in numerous career paths (Ramdass & Zimmerman, 2011). They denoted several self-regulation skills, such as time management, setting goals, effort and persistence in completing difficult tasks, or self-monitoring one’s performance.

Schunk, Pintrich, & Meece (2008) also described self-regulation as a process by which learners activate cognitions and behaviours to reach their goals. Similarly, these authors underlined the relevance of becoming a self-regulated student to achieve success in academic spheres and in other areas of the life.

As can be observed, there is not a unique definition of self-regulation. Wirth and Leutner (2008) pointed out ten years ago that although many models of self-regulation have been proposed in the last years, a theoretical framework that integrates them all in a coherent manner was missing. Nowadays it is possible to repeat the same statement; the different models have not been integrated in a coherent framework. Nevertheless, all the formulated models addressed the relevance of self-regulation for learning. The main models of self-regulation have been formulated by Zimmerman (2000); Pintrich (2000); Boekaerts (2011); Efklides (2011); Hadwin, Järvelä and Miller (2011) and Winne (2011); differing in the phases and subprocesses included, the main explored areas (metacognition, motivation or emotion), and in the way of conceptualizing several aspects (Panadero, 2017).

One of the models most referred to is Zimmerman's (2000) one. It includes several cognitive abilities that can be converted into academic skills by the self-regulation process, such as adopting powerful strategies for attaining goals, monitoring one's performance in order to find indications of advancement or failure, managing one's time use efficiently, self-evaluating the employed methods to know their effectiveness and adapting the unsuccessful ones. The author distinguished three stages in a self-regulation process: forethought phase, performance phase and self-reflection phase. In the different phases, the student should carry out different self-regulatory processes. These processes include task analysis, self-observation and self-judgement of one's execution, self-control of that execution, etc. The first phase occurs before facing a task, when organizing it. The last one takes place after completing the task, when reflecting on one's execution.

The aim of this research was to investigate the factors influencing learning during the process of solving a task, specifically the speed factor. Therefore, in this work an emphasis is laid on the performance phase, when self-control and self-observation are

supposed to play a major role (Zimmerman, 2002). In the performance phase, the students actually execute the task so they must monitor their progress and adapt their strategies to complete the task successfully: For example, checking the effectiveness of each response, controlling global response speed and adjusting it, represent relevant strategies to be carried out in this stage. These actions of self-evaluation occur not only at the end of the activity but also during its progress and are indispensable for making the necessary adjustments during the execution. Then, the student can initiate regulatory activities such as adjusting the execution speed. This phase is specially demanding because the student should execute the task and, simultaneously, self-observe and self-control the execution (DiBenedetto & Zimmerman, 2010).

Several studies have shown that self-regulatory processes are highly related to academic success. During the 1970s and 1980s, several researchers studied the influence of self-regulatory processes and discovered that these strategies were generally effective in producing superior learning, even with young children (Zimmerman, 2008). Besides, several authors using self-reports and interviews showed that self-regulated learning was correlated to academic performance (Zimmerman & Martinez- Pons, 1986, 1990; Pintrich, Smith, Garcia & McKeachie, 1993). At the same time, Britton and Tesser (1991) carried out a longitudinal study using a time management questionnaire. These researchers verified the effects of time management practices on academic achievement during the college years. The participants answered the questionnaire when entering to the university and then answered it again four years later, when finishing their studies. The results indicated that self-reports of time management were positively related to academic achievement four years later at their graduation. Trueman and Hartley (1996) also tested the relation between time management scores in a 14-items Likert-type scale and academic performance at university. They reported a significant relation.

DiBenedetto and Zimmerman (2010) compared the practice of self-regulatory processes of students that obtained high and low marks. When students were completing a task, they were asked about the self-control and self-observation processes they were carrying out. They found that high achieving students used significantly more self-control strategies while solving the task than low achieving students did. Besides, the quality of the high achievers self-monitoring was significantly higher than that of the low and average achievers. Similarly, Cleary and Chen (2009) confirmed that the use of self-regulation strategies reliably differentiated high achievers and low achievers in academically rigorous or intensive math classrooms. Nevertheless, they highlighted that this relation only appears in environments that require high levels of self-discipline and persistence, like in advanced math courses.

Interventions in self-regulation and time management

During the school years, teachers play a main role in regulating students' learning by setting goals, managing their time while solving tasks, administering homework, etc. Then, when students pass to next grades, teachers gradually reduce their help and expect students to incorporate these processes of self-regulation (Ramdass & Zimmerman, 2011).

Nevertheless, even at the university, many students lack self-regulation strategies (Cazan, 2013). The good news is that apparently, these self-regulation strategies can be learned (Lavasani, Mirhosseini, Hejazi & Davoodi, 2011; Cazan, 2013) and interventions to encourage self-regulated learning are successful ways to improve student's learning as long as they are properly designed (Panadero, 2017). Ramdass and Zimmerman (2011) noted that self-regulatory student's behaviours develop gradually over time with repeated practice. In addition, they revealed that self-regulatory training could be effectively

applied to primary school children through classrooms activities and homework to enable students to use time management skills.

Terry (2002) carried out an experimental procedure using a web tool to incite university students to self-monitoring their time. The tool gave feedback to the students about their time-management behaviors for two weeks. The study was based on Schunk's (1994) model, which consider three components of self-regulation during the performance stage: self-observation of one's performance, self-judgement to analyze whether this behavior is helping to attach one's goals and self-reaction to change one's performance if necessary. Although Terry found no significant improvement in self-regulation scale results or in math performance after the program, data suggested that interventions that lead to changes in time management behaviors would result in changes in self-regulated learning behaviors.

Stoeger and Ziegler (2008) developed and implemented a classroom-based training to improve self-regulation in time management tasks in elementary students. After the training, students in the experimental group evidenced improved time management skills and self-reflection of their own learning in comparison to the control group.

Besides, several studies have analysed the effect of therapies focused on self-regulation strategies for people suffering of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). These interventions aim at improving self-regulation processes among ADHD students and therefore promote their academic success (Braswell & Bloomquist, 1991; Haig, 2012). Murray (2002) successfully introduced cognitive-behavioural methods for training self-control techniques to pre-school children with impulsive behaviours. Likewise, Heinrich, Gevensleben, Freisleder, Moll and Rothenberger (2004) examined the effect of teaching self-control techniques on elementary students with ADHD and

found improvements in children's behaviour and a decrease in the severity of their disorder. A meta-analysis by Reid, Trout and Schwartz (2005) confirmed that self-monitoring interventions as a useful component in an intervention program for children with ADHD. The results showed that self-regulated interventions engendered meaningful improvements in ADHD students for academic productivity, on-task behaviour, and reduction of inappropriate behaviours.

As a result of the described studies, research revealed that elementary school children and college students are capable of acquiring self-regulatory skills (Schunk and Swartz 1993a, 1993b; Schunk and Zimmerman, 2003; Stoeger and Ziegler 2005) and that self-regulation behaviors can be developed and trained. Students may learn to evaluate and monitor their behaviours and to perform effectively and productively even in the absence of an external agent (e.g. parent, teacher, principal) (Beh-Pajooh, Fatemi, Bonab, Alizadeh, Hemmati, 2012).

Measures of self-regulation and empirical evidence

Several measures aiming to assess self-regulation have been proposed. Winne and Perry (2000) highlighted two alternative approaches of conceiving self-regulation that imply different ways of measurement: self-regulation can be conceived as an aptitude or as an event. Those authors who conceive self-regulation as an aptitude consider it as an ability that someone possess, that makes it possible to predict how people will act in the future. This approach usually employs measures such as self-reports, interviews or teacher judgements. Hence, these instruments express the estimated level of the student's ability to self-regulate according students or teacher's reports. On the other side, self-regulation is conceived as an event, which is the self-regulated behavior that a person do in a determinate moment while solving a determinate task. Task characteristics (context, stimuli, feedback, instructions, etc.) are expected to influence in the process of self-

regulation. Within this approach, the measures aim to assess the self-regulation process in the moment that it occurs for example, through think aloud measures, error detection tasks, trace methodologies or direct observations of performance. Trace measures have been defined as “observable indicators about cognition that students create as they engage in a task” (Winne & Perry, 2000, p.551), for example, an annotation that a student makes while studying. Several researchers also employed structured personal diaries (Schmitz & Wiese, 2006) or direct observations of regulatory behaviours in particular contexts (Perry, 1998). This technology may serve as a base to design computerized tests that record these measures easily.

Winne and Jamieson-Noel (2002) reported that self-reports are often inconsistent with trace measures of self-regulatory processes as a result of their studies comparing self-regulated behaviours reported through self-reports and recordings of actual self-regulation traces while students work in a task by using an innovative software program called gStudy. Nevertheless, despite technological advances in the last decades, self-report scales represent the most widely used self-regulatory measure (Cleary, Callan & Zimmerman, 2012), mostly due to economic reasons. Dinsmore, Alexander and Loughlin (2008) also highlighted this fact expressing their concern about the existing heavy reliance on self-reports and the insufficient corroboration with actual traces of people’s behaviours. Many researchers have questioned the validity of self-report measures to assess self-regulation (Winne & Perry, 2000; Winne & Jamieson-Noel, 2002; Crombach, Boekaerts & Voeten, 2003; Veenman, Prins & Verheij, 2003; Veenman, 2011). These concerns have also been addressed when assessing other psychological factors such as personality variables (Santacreu, Rubio & Hernández, 2006; Ortner & Schmitt, 2014; Ortner & Proyer, 2018). Even researchers that used self-report measures in their studies acknowledge possible flaws of using it (Britton & Tesser, 1991). Some authors have

proposed objective tests as an alternative measure of several psychological variables as abilities and personality variables (Santacreu, Rubio & Hernández, 2006; Ortner & Schmitt, 2014; Ortner & Proyer, 2015). Cattell (1946) generated the first generation of this kind of measures. Several objective tests have been developed in the last years, conforming a way of obtaining “information about a person’s characteristics by assessing their behaviour in a highly standardized miniature situation” (Ortner & Proyer, 2015, p.6).

Turner (1995) highlighted the existence of several advantages of using direct observations of behaviour to measure self-regulated learning. First, they are a manifestation of what students actually do instead of what they remember or consider that they do. Besides, these performance observations are related to a concrete task, so it is possible to analyse the influence of several task factors in performance such as the presence or absence of feedback.

Based on these considerations, Quiroga, Santacreu, Montoro, Martínez-Molina and Shih (2011) developed a computerized objective learning test that can offer a direct observation of self-regulation processes, the Category Learning Test (CLT). In this task, test takers are instructed to learn which tokens are associated to the highest score to click on it and therefore, to gain points. Unlike other category learning tasks, the CLT was designed and configured to assess not only the level of learning achieved but also the evolution of the execution patterns that participants display during the task. In each trial, there 150 figures were presented simultaneously with up to 30 elements belonging to the target category. By contrast to the serial stimuli presentation, the CLT stimuli presentation enables test takers to explore around the screen during the trial length. The simultaneous presentation of all the stimuli enables the participant to execute a variable number of responses during the trial and means that different patterns of response are possible. Furthermore, this set-up gives more ecological validity to the task because of its similarity

to real life, where many elements appear together with others and the response options are not dichotomous, but multiple and variable. Therefore, we consider that this task is an adequate task to assess self-regulation learning.

Based on a study including children aged between 7 and 12 years, Santacreu and Quiroga (2016) discovered that one third of the sample did not learn the target category. Besides, they found that the proportion of correct clicks, i.e. Learning Index, was significantly related to the studied execution variables: organization, i.e., the scanning of the screen following an ordered pattern ($r = 0.68$) and speed, i.e. interval between responses ($r = 0.53$). Hence, when students acted slowly and organized, they succeeded to learn what the target category was. These results seem to be related to self-regulation learning, since there were a great numbers of students that presumably did not self-monitor or self-control their response speed and organization to achieve the task's goals. The authors argued that these students might be behaving in the same way when undertaking school tasks and therefore their school performance may be deficient.

In line with Winne and Perry (2000), results gained by the CLT were considered as an event and as an aptitude at the same time. Some CLT variables as the speed index or the pattern of responses could be conceived as a direct measure of self-regulated behaviours, framed within the conception of self-regulated as an event. Despite of that, the authors that employed it consider that performance on the CLT could be related to academic performance, because students might behave in the same way while solving the CLT and solving academic tasks. Therefore, this is way of conceiving self-regulation as an aptitude. As Winne and Perry (2000) proposed, a model that conceive self-regulation as an event and as an aptitude at the same time is possible. These authors explained that mental factors have an influence, but also environmental factors do. Certainly, environmental variables of the task as the disposition of the stimuli, proportion of targets,

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time or feedback influence the student's self-regulated behavior, in the same way as the individual's previous personal abilities. Thus, we propose in this study that CLT assesses actual self-regulation process in that concrete task. However, simultaneously we consider that this measure is an indicator of typical behavior and is therefore able to predict future behaviors. Besides, we consider that the environment has an influence such as this self-regulated behavior can be trained, what increases the importance of assessing it.

The aim of the present study

In short, the present study aims at studying the relation between the speed with which a task is solved and the level of learning that is achieved in this task. As indicated by studies above (e.g., Terry, 2002; Stoeger and Ziegler, 2008), time represents a key component in self-regulation. Students showing higher levels of self-regulation usually monitor their response speed during a task and adjust their speed if it is necessary to achieve their goals.

Whereas many students start to perform effectively and productively even in the absence of an external agent (e.g. parent, teacher, principal) when grown up (Ramdass & Zimmerman, 2011; Beh-Pajoooh, et al., 2012), some students do not succeed at learning to self-regulate without an external support even at college. The main hypothesis of this research formulates that when introducing an external limitation of speed, individuals who are not initially able to self-regulate their response speed, will decrease it and then they will achieve a higher learning index.

In line with this aim, we firstly conducted a pilot study to analyse the response speed of adults who achieved to learn in the original version of the task, in comparison with the response speed of those who did not learn. Based on this information, in the second study, we aimed at introducing an external regulation of the response speed of part of the sample, conforming the experimental group. We established a speed limit in order to force their response speed to be similar to the optimal speed found in the first

study. Our first hypothesis stated that the speed limitation group would be related to a better performance in the task.

Secondly, we expected to find a great proportion of high-performance participants and a lower proportion of low-performance participants in the experimental group than in the control group. However, since university students formed the sample and should be able to self-regulate, we expected to find high achievers also in the control group.

Lastly, we analysed the response speed of high and low achievers throughout the trials in order to know whether it was related to the differences in the learning index of participants in the control group. We expected high-performers to act slower than low-performers.

STUDY 1

Method

Participants

Forty-one undergraduates enrolled in a Psychology Degree in a public university in Spain volunteered for course credit to complete an assessment procedure. Twenty-one were in the first year, fifteen were in the second year, three were in the third year and one was in the last year. They were aged between 18 and 24, and, on average, the participants were 19.4 years old ($SD=1.17$). Thirty-eight participants were women and three were men.

Materials

All the participants completed a short version of the Category Learning Test (CLT, Quiroga et al., 2011). The CLT seems to be an adequate task to analyse some self-

regulation behaviours such as adjustment of speed, as explained above. The focus was on the actual self-regulated behaviours that a student executes while solving a task.

This task version consisted of eight trials and each trial lasted 14 seconds. Each participant completed the eight trials. Each trial consisted of a 15 by 15 matrix (225 squares), on which 105 different figures were displayed simultaneously. When the participant clicked on a figure, the screen immediately showed the number of points scored i.e. 9, 3, 1 or 0 points. This matrix contained 30 target tokens featuring four legged animals valued 9 points and 75 non-target tokens featuring other figures (vegetables, living-beings, means of transport...), 21 of which were worth 3 points, 20 were worth 1 point, and 34 tokens had 0 value. The instructions of the task informed test-takers that the aim was to identify and click on the figures associated with the best prize in order to get the highest score.

Figure 1 demonstrated a CLT item illustrating the screen displaying the scored earned when clicking on the token. The timer was present in every item, on the right side of the screen.

[Insert Figure 1 about here]

The CLT registered the click type i.e. which figure was clicked on, and the time (milliseconds) when the click occurred.

Variables

The following variables were obtained for each trial:

1. Hits: H, the number of 9-point tokens clicked on.
2. Non optimal responses: NOR, the number of clicks on 3-point, 1-point or 0-point tokens.
3. Learning Index: LI, the ratio of hits to the total number of clicks.
4. Speed response: the number of clicks per second.

Procedure

Student volunteers that wanted to participate in the study chose one of the different appointments available. All of them participated for course credit but they could achieve this credit in other ways. At the start of the study, the participants were briefly informed about the study avoiding biasing the results. They were told that the procedure aimed at assessing different competences. They signed an informed consent document to participate in the investigation. After the assessment, they were fully informed about the study.

Participants completed the task in the IT room being supervised by two psychologists. Before starting the task, they read the instructions on their computers.

Once the data was recorded, each participants' scores were calculated for each trial. Statistical analysis were performed using SPSS Statistics 24.0 package.

Results

According to the first research question, we analysed whether two groups of persons showing different learning behaviour during the task that could be distinguished statistically. Hence, we carried out a cluster analysis of profiles (SPSS K-Means procedure) to classify individuals in two groups based on the level of learning achieved during the eight trials. We found that 29 students that learnt the target category during the task composed the first group (High Learning Group, HLG). They obtained, in average, an LI of 0.8. Therefore, 80% of their answers was correct. 12 people that obtained, in average, an LI of 0.39, formed the second group (Low Learning Group, LLG). Hence, only 39% of their answers were correct, a proportion that is near to the expected by chance in this task.

According to the second question, we analysed differences in response speed in both groups in order to check whether the learning index was associated with a lower

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response speed. Therefore, once we classified people depending of their LIs, we compared the response speed of these two groups, considering the number of clicks executed during each trial that lasted 14 seconds. The Independent Samples T-Test showed significant differences between the two groups in the average number of clicks executed during each trial ($t(15) = -5.44, p < .001$). The group that obtained a high LI executed, in average, one click every 0.86 seconds (Speed Index = 1.17, SD = .27). The group that obtained a low LI executed, in average, one click every 0.54 seconds (Speed Index = 1.85, SD = .46).

STUDY 2

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of one hundred and eighty-four university students aged between 18 and 30. On average, they were 20.17 years old (SD=2.03). One hundred and fifty-one participants were women and thirty-three were men. As in the study 1, all the participants were studying a Psychology Degree in a public university in Spain. Eighty-five were in the first year, fifty-seven were in the second year, twenty-nine were in the third year and thirteen were in the last year. One hundred and fifty-one participants were women and thirty-three were men.

Materials

All the students completed a long version of the Category Learning Test (CLT, Quiroga et al., 2011). The task was almost the same that the one described in the first study, but the duration of the trials was longer in this study: each trial lasted 25 seconds.

Variables

The variables calculated were the same as in the first study.

Design

Test-takers were randomly assigned either to the experimental or to the control group. Finally, due to some initial dropouts, the distribution of the groups was ninety-nine participants in the experimental group and eighty-five in the control group.

In the experimental group, a speed limit was introduced in order to force their response speed to be similar to the optimal speed found in the first study. Hence, we compared the performance of two similar groups in the task: the experimental group was presented a version of CLT with a speed limitation and the control group was presented the task without any speed limitation to let participants to respond as fast as they wanted. Considering the results of the first study, the speed limitation applied consisted of a maximum of 1 click per second. The speed limitation was applied by deactivating the mouse during 1 second after each click: the mouse pointer disappeared during that time.

We amplified the original trial duration to 25 seconds in order that participants have enough time to explore the tokens and learn despite the speed limitation of the experimental condition. Therefore, in this study, the trials lasted 25 seconds in both conditions.

Procedure

As in the study 1, before the start of the study, student volunteers were briefly informed that the procedure aimed at assessing different competences. Again, all of them participated for course credit but they could achieve this credit in other ways. They signed an informed consent document. After the assessment, they were fully informed about the study.

Participants completed the task in the IT room being supervised by two psychologists. Before starting the task, the instructions were presented on their computers.

Once the data was recorded, each participants' scores were calculated for each trial. Again, statistical analyses were performed using SPSS Statistics 24.0 package.

Results

In order to check whether our intervention worked by reducing the speed in the experimental group, we firstly analysed the differences in the speed index between the experimental and the control groups. The results of the Independent Samples T-test revealed significant differences between the two groups in the average speed index executed during the task ($t(86) = 17.84, p < .001$). The average speed index for the control group was 1.36 (SD=0.43) clicks per second, while the speed index for the experimental group was 0.53 (SD=0.05) clicks per second. This result meant that the experimental group was clicking slower than the control group: the experimental group click in average every 1.89 seconds and the control group do it every 0.74 seconds. Therefore, the speed limitation had the expected effect on working speed. It is also remarkable the high standard deviation in the control group.

Afterwards, we analysed whether these differences in the speed index were related to a higher average LI in the experimental group. The Independent Samples T-test revealed significant differences between the two groups in the average learning index obtained during the task ($t(150) = -6.63, p < .001$). The control group achieved in average a LI of 0.69 (SD=0.2) during the task and the experimental group obtained in average an LI of 0.87 (SD=0.14).

Secondly, we carried out a cluster analysis of profiles (SPSS K-Means procedure) to classify individuals in two groups based on the level of learning achieved during the eight trials. There were 145 participants that learned the target category, achieving a high LI (LI=0.87, SD=0.08) and 39 participants that did not learn the target category, obtaining a low LI (LI=0.46, SD=0.14). In order to check the experimental condition participants were assigned to, we carried out a contingency table (see Table 2). As expected, the Chi-squared test revealed that there were significant differences in distribution among the groups ($\chi^2(3, N=184) = 32.359, p < .001$), showing a relation between the presence of the speed limitation and the learning group to which one belonged. In the control group, 38.8% of the participants did not manage to learn the target categories. This percentage decreases to 6.1% in those participants whose response speed was limited, i.e. in the experimental group. Hence, in the experimental group, there was a higher proportion of people who achieved a high LI than in the control group. Most of the participants (93.9%) in the experimental group learned, in comparison with 61.2% of the participants in the control group that achieved a high LI.

Table 2. *Distribution of participants between the learning groups and conditions.*

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Total
<i>High Learning Group</i>	93	52	145
<i>Low Learning Group</i>	6	33	39
<i>Total</i>	99	85	184

According to the second hypothesis, we analysed the speed index of these groups throughout the trials. The low learning group (LLG) in the control condition acted too fast, maintaining a speed index near to 2 clicks per second ($\bar{X} = 1.72, SD = .46$) (see figure

2). By contrast, the high learning group (HLG) in the control condition maintained a lower speed index ($\bar{X}=1.12$, $SD=.16$) despite of not having any limitation. The t-test showed significant differences in the speed index between these two groups of the control condition ($t(37) = -7.233$, $p < .001$). On the other hand, as expected due to the speed limitation, both groups in the experimental condition maintained a low speed index near to 0.5 click per second, lower than the maximum allowed (LLG: $\bar{X}=0.52$, $SD=.05$; HLG: $\bar{X}=0.53$, $SD=.05$; no significant differences between them).

Figure 2. Average speed index by trials, learning groups and conditions.

*Control-HL: high learning group in control condition; Control-LL: low learning group in control condition; Exp-HL: high learning group in experimental condition; Exp-LL: low learning group in experimental condition.

DISCUSSION

This study was to investigate the relation between response speed while solving a task and learning. Specifically, we aimed to know if an external limitation of the response speed could foster learning for students who was not able to self-regulate their response speed.

The first study revealed that the response speed was highly related to the level of learning achieved in a category learning task. In this study, the students that achieved a

high proportion of hits, acted slower than the participants that achieved a lower proportion of hits. In the CLT, the test-taker should click on different figures, exploring the number of points associated with each figure. By following this method, they could check different hypothesis: are the vegetables the figures associated to the highest prize? Are all the living beings? Are just the animals? Which kind of animal? Hence, by clicking on the figures, they could learn the number of points associated with each figure and then deduce the category associated with the higher number of points, in this case, the mammals. It is not possible to know certainly the learning process that the participants were following, but it is possible to observe the result of this process, i.e. the number of target tokens that have been clicked. Since participants in the HLG achieved a proportion of 90% correct answers it is logical to think that they knew the classification criteria, they learnt which the target category was. Participants in the LLG presumably did not have time enough between each click to pay attention to the score obtained and associated it to each figure, and then to deduce which was the target category. Despite of that, they did not decrease their speed. They did not self-regulate their behaviour: they did not self-monitor or self-adjust their execution to be able to improve their learning index.

As Schunk and Zimmerman (1994) stated, the act of monitoring one's performance to find signs of success or failure as well as the adaptation of the strategies when are not useful is key for achieving superior learning. In our first study, it is clear how students that adopted an adequate response speed achieved to learn while students that were not self-assessing or self-adjusting their response speed were not able to learn the classification criteria.

Ramdass and Zimmerman (2011) indicated that during the childhood there is an external regulation from teachers. When students grow up, they start to integrate these strategies and start to self-regulate. However, even at the university, many students lack

self-regulation strategies in absence of an external agent (Cazan, 2013). In the first study, several university students did not self-regulate and did not learn the target category. Therefore, we aimed at investigating whether an external regulation could help these students to learn.

With this aim, a speed limit was applied to the experimental group in the second study, aiming at promoting learning. The results showed that the speed limitation had the desired effect: students in the experimental group, in average, acted slower and achieved a higher learning index than students in the control group. Hence, the speed limitation promoted learning.

However, it should be noted that some people in the control group were able to self-regulate without the external control: they acted slowly and achieved a high learning index. In contrast, approximately the 39% of the control group acted too quickly to learn without the speed limitation. Therefore, not every student needs this external control, as could be expected since university students formed the sample. The external control seems to be only favourable for students that are not able to self-regulate. It should be noted that self-regulated learning is not just acting slowly but also adapting other strategies that are not being useful. However, acting slowly could allow students to introduce some of these adaptive strategies.

Therefore, the results of the second study could be interpreted in a way that adapting the environment for some students, for example, establishing the time that they are provided to solve each exercise in an exam in order to decrease their speed while solving the exercises, could be helpful for them. However, we consider that it is more important to train these students to make them able to adapt themselves to the environment instead of adapting the environment for them. In this way, Ramdass & Zimmerman (2011) remarked the relevance of implementing self-regulation training

programs since it could be possible to increase the frequency of self-regulation behaviours, what is a key element for academic success. The present study shed light on how some students could be not having trouble at academic spheres because being unable to self-regulate their speed while solving the tasks. This result could be used in order to propose training programs to promote self-regulation of response speed. In this regard, in future studies it would be interesting to check if after completing several tasks with a speed limitation, the test-takers start to self-regulate their speed in another task. In addition, the instructions and/or the feedback of the task could encourage them to self-regulate their speed.

With regard to the conception of self-regulation, this work showed how the environment, in this case the characteristics of the task, has an influence on self-regulated learning. Besides, the CLT is a test that assessed actual self-regulated behaviors while solving the task. Therefore, the approach of this study could be related to the conception of self-regulation as an event, an individual's performance in a specific moment and task. However, as Winne and Perry (2000) proposed, we consider that it is possible to conceive self-regulation as an aptitude at the same time. We expect that students that acted too fast to learn in the CLT will act in a similar way when solving other tasks. In addition, as explained above, we consider that training self-regulation is possible. Therefore, the approach of this paper is similar to the one raised by Winne and Perry (2000).

Furthermore, it is remarkable the usefulness of objective tests. The CLT has provided information about each click that each participant did, so made it possible to know the number of hits and mistakes but also the response speed, resulting a relevant variable related to learning. Therefore, it is possible to assess the actual behaviors of a student instead of just counting on the estimations that the student makes about his/her usual behavior. This is becoming more important since Winne and Jamieson-Noel (2002)

revealed that self-reports are often inconsistent with records of actual self-regulation processes and several authors have questioned the validity of self-report measures to assess self-regulation and other psychological variables (Crombach, Boekaerts & Voeten, 2003; Veenman, Prins & Verheij, 2003; Veenman, 2011; Winne & Jamieson-Noel, 2002; Winne & Perry, 2000). In addition, as Turner (1995) stated, using direct observations of performance allows the analysis of the influence of task factors. Actually, because of being able to introduce a speed limit it has been possible to value the influence of response speed on learning. Besides, modifying other characteristics of the CLT such as the instructions or the feedback would make it possible to value the influence of these factors in self-regulated learning.

There are some limitations to this study. On the one hand, we consider that the time of speed limitation applied was too long to our goal. We intended the experimental group to perform at a similar speed than the HLG in the first study, approximately clicking one token per second. In contrast, due to the speed limitation, the experimental group ended up acting too slow, clicking about one token each two seconds, lower than necessary.

On the other hand, the size of the sample in the first study could be considered small. However, we would like to highlight how in the control condition of the second study, the LLG acted as quickly as the LLG in the first study. The same occurred with both HLGs, whose speed indexes were similar in the first study and in the control condition of the second one. Therefore, the sample of the first study seemed to be enough to assess the learning and speed indexes and was representative of a bigger population.

As a conclusion, it should be noted that the response speed is highly relevant for learning. In addition, it is clear that an external regulation of the response speed could

promote learning to the students that do not self-regulate their response speed. Nevertheless, this result should be interpreted in a way that training self-regulation, especially of the response speed, might be beneficial for some students even at university. Moreover, the utility of objective test such as the CLT to assess self-regulation behaviours and their relation to learning is manifest.

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